

A CASE REPORT MINICORE MYOPATHY IN ASSOCIATION WITH EXTERNAL OPHTHALMOPLEGIA

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ABSTRACT:

Minicore myopathy is a very rare inherited muscle condition that causes muscle weakness and atrophy. It gets its name from the tiny 'core' structures seen when looking at muscle cells under a microscope, as well as the word 'myopathy,' which means muscular ailment. The 8-year-old male patient was presented to the OPD with symptoms of exhaustion, trouble walking over the last 10-15 days, and a sudden start of discomfort in the contralateral lower limb in the popliteal region that became increasingly intense and intensified, as well as widespread muscular weakness. Specialized Diagnostic Tests was done for Genomic DNA testing from blood sample and report said that patient was likely to be affected with minicore myopathy with external ophthalmoplegia due to presence of heterozygous status for c.8518C > T in exon 54 of the RYR1 gene. Primary diagnosis was minicore myopathy with external ophthalmoplegia. External ophthalmoplegia is a myopathic sign of mitochondrial disease that can appear in a range of clinical manifestations. However, one important take-away lesson from this report is that early detection of EO by a vigilant physician can help in the proper diagnosis of multi-organ mitochondrial sequelae, leading in lesser morbidity and mortality in these patients.

KEY WORDS:

Minicore myopathy

External ophthalmoplegia

Pediatrics

Rhinodine receptor

RYR1 gene mutation.

INTRODUCTION:

Minicore myopathy is an uncommon genetic muscle disorder that results in muscular atrophy and weakening. Its name comes from the microscopic 'core' structures that may be observed when looking at muscle cells under a microscope, as well as the word 'myopathy,' which meaning muscle illness. Prevalence is not known. Congenital myopathies are a group of muscular disorders that occur at birth. The term "congenital" refers to a condition that exists from birth. Minicore myopathy is a very diverse disorder, with varying degrees of severity and rates of advancement in various persons. Minicore myopathy symptoms are frequently present from birth, however diagnosis may not occur for several years. Symptoms can appear at any age, even maturity. Minicore myopathy is a hereditary disorder produced by a mistake in the DNA (also known as a 'mutation'). Minicore myopathy is caused by mutations in two genes termed SEPN1 and RYR1. The instructions for making the 'ryanodine receptor 1' protein are found in the RYR1 gene. Other kinds of congenital myopathy are known to be caused by mutations in the RYR1 gene, including central core disease and congenital fiber-type disproportion. This disorder is frequently inherited in an autosomal recessive form, which means that two mutated genes are passed down from mother to father. A person with an autosomal recessive condition has one copy of the defective gene in each parent, but they normally show no signs or symptoms of the disease. If both parents are carriers, a kid has a 25% chance of inheriting the disease, or 1 in 4. The symptoms of minicore myopathy are highly variable from person to person and to some extent depend on what the genetic cause is, as described above. Although there is no cure for minicore myopathy, a multidisciplinary team of health specialists can assist manage the symptoms. Floppiness (hypotonia) and muscular weakness, particularly in the muscles nearest to the body, are the most common symptoms. Motor milestones that are delayed, such as sitting alone and crawling, are frequently the first signs that anything is amiss. Physiotherapy can assist to maintain muscular function and avoid contractures, especially in the Achilles tendon. The tightness of the muscular tendons hinders limb and joint mobility. Doctors may be drawn to the youngster because of his or her inability to flourish. This failure to gain weight might be due to eating issues, but it's also possible that a lack of muscular mass and the extra energy spent by people with muscle weakness merely conducting day-to-day

activities play a role. Minicore myopathy is also characterised by a tight or stiff spine, as well as a curvature of the spine (scoliosis).¹

Only for the congenital myopathies as a group, not for specific disorders, are epidemiological statistics accessible. All congenital myopathies are expected to account for 0.06 per 1,000 live births, or one tenth of all neuromuscular diseases. Multi-minicore Disease (MmD) is a muscle biopsy-based histopathological diagnosis. Multifocal, well-circumscribed regions with reduced oxidative staining and decreased myofibrillar ATPase define MmD. Following eccentric exercise, healthy probands have been reported to have minicores as a non-specific result on muscle biopsy (i.e., lengthening during activity) All families and individuals who have been diagnosed with MmD should receive genetic counselling. Only a few families with multi-minicores on muscle biopsy and dominant inheritance have been described. The majority of cases connected to mutations in the RYR1 gene and SEPN1-related MmD are inherited as an autosomal recessive disease.² Neuromuscular illnesses are a diverse set of disorders that are frequently hereditary. They are categorised into problems that affect the anterior horn cell, peripheral nerve, neuromuscular junction, and muscle strain in general. Myotonic dystrophy and mitochondrial myopathies are examples of multisystem illnesses that are routinely covered.³ External ophthalmoplegia is a symptom in a myopathy that is characterised by progressive bilateral ptosis and a widespread loss in ocular movement. instead of an accurate diagnosis EO is frequently associated with additional systemic signs and symptoms of mitochondrial malfunction, which can result in substantial morbidity and death. Gradual external ophthalmoplegia is a descriptive clinical finding rather than a diagnosis, characterised by progressive bilateral ptosis and widespread, symmetric loss in ocular movement. While ophthalmoplegia is often asymptomatic in EO, ptosis is not. Visual obstruction is common in myopathic ptosis, forcing patients to adopt an extremely uncomfortable compensatory chin-up position with constant frontalis contraction to maintain their vision.⁴

LIST OF ABBREVIATION:

NICU – Newborn Intensive Care Unit

CIAB – Cried Immediately After Birth

FTVD – Full Term Vaginal Delivery

MRC – Medical Research Centre

EO – External ophthalmoplegia

MmD – Multi minicore Disease

BPM – Beats per minute

MUAC – Mid upper arm circumference

CASE REPORT:

On 28th July 2021, 8 year old male patient came to OPD with complaints of fatigue, difficulty in walking since 10-15 days, sudden onset of pain in bilateral lower limb in popliteal region that was progressively severe and intensifying, generalized muscle weakness.

On examining the patient pulse rate was 102 BPM Temperature was normal blood pressure 102/64mmHg on cardiovascular examination S1 S2 were present with no murmur on respiratory examination no any added sound were there respiratory rate was 24/minute. Patient was conscious and oriented and active.

Developmental history cranial nerve growth was normal, Height was 110cm, Head circumference Was 50 cm, Weight was 14 kg, MUAC was 15 cm.

Birth History of patient FTVD/Home Delivery/Birth Weight 2.5kg/CIAB/No NICU.

Family history patient's father was employee in private company and mother was housewife and two elder sisters (14 y/o & 12 y/o) were there.

There was no any major medical condition or illness in patient's family.

On Examination left upper limb was weakened right upper limb was normal but in lower limb involuntary movement was present, mild atrophy of right lower limb was noted, planter reflex were present.

On assessment of MRC muscle strength/power grade 4 was given to both upper limb and lower limb also.

Following laboratory parameters were found, Blood was obtained for laboratory analysis, specifically, the following values were measured: Haemoglobin, 11 g/dL (reference range, 12-17.5 g/dL); Red blood cells, 4.8 million per cubic millimeter (reference range, 4.2-6.1 million per cubic millimeter); Neutrophils, 72% (reference range, 40-80%); Lymphocytes, 26% (reference range, 20-40%); Monocytes, 1% (reference range, 2-10%); Eosinophils, 1% (reference range, 1-2%); Packed cell volume, 34.50% (reference range, 40-56%); Albumin, 4.1g/dl (reference range, 3.5-5.5g/dl); Globulin 2.2g/dl (reference range, 2.0-3.9g/dl); Urea, 22mg/dl (reference range, 14-40mg/dl); Ser. Creatinine 0.52mg/dl (reference range, 0.50-1.2mg/dl).

Other laboratory tests like Ser. Troponin, Ser. CK MB, CSF (Plasma & Protein) were normal.

Specialized Diagnostic Tests: - Genomic DNA testing from blood sample

Interpretation – The patient is likely to be affected with minicore myopathy with external ophthalmoplegia due to presence of heterozygous status for c.8518C > T in exone 54 of the RYR1 gene.

Other Diagnostic tests: - Magnetic resonance Imaging – Normal,

CRP – 6 mg/l,

Dengue Non structural-1 Antigen – Negative.

TREATMENT CHART:

Generic Name	Dose	Route	Frequency	Days Given
T.MV BC	1 capsule	PO	1-0-1	1-6 Days
T. Ca ⁺² + Vit.D3	500mg+500IU	PO	1-0-1	1-6 Days
T. Folic Acid	5 mg	PO	1-0-1	1-6 Days
T. Gabapentin	100 mg	PO	1-0-1/2	4-9 Days
T. Biotin	10 mg	PO	1-0-1	4-9 Days
T. Thiamine	100 mg	PO	1-1-1	4-9 Days
Syp. Carnisure	2-3 ml	PO	q6hr	4-9 Days
T. Pyridoxine	40 mg	PO	1-0-0	6-9 Days
Syp. Levocet	3 ml	PO	HS	6-9 Days

DISCUSSION:

Here we report one paediatric patient with minicore myopathy, with complaints of fatigue, difficulty in walking since 10-15 days, sudden onset of pain in bilateral lower limb in popliteal region that was progressively severe and intensifying, generalized muscle weakness. The other three clinical traits are uncommon, and they are as follows: a) Due to significant prenatal akinesia, antenatal onset with arthrogryposis occurs, with dysmorphic characteristics and congenital widespread arthrogryposis. b) Gradually increasing fatigueness with significant hand amyotrophy, with marked upper limb distal weakness, amyotrophy of intrinsic hand muscles, and virtually normal lower limb distal muscles. c) External ophthalmoplegia of varying degree, as well as widespread muscle involvement comparable to that described for the classical variety, characterises the ophthalmoplegic variant. Facial weakness is considerable in this ophthalmic type. This disease can be diagnosed by muscle biopsy, Predominance of type I fibres and the existence of well-defined cores with loss of intermyofibrillary mitochondrial activity as seen in the present instances, are some of the distinguishing characteristics. ⁽⁶⁾ Studies on molecular genetics are now being developed. Genetic heterogeneity appears to underpin the phenotypic diversity of multi-minicore illness, according to preliminary results of genetic investigations published in the literature. ⁽⁷⁾ There are no any specific treatment for this disease but this disease should be monitored closely by specialist and further evaluations are needed for prevention of lethal complication.

CONCLUSION:

Minicore myopathy is an uncommon genetic muscle disorder that results in muscular atrophy and weakening. Its name comes from the microscopic 'core' structures that may be observed when looking at muscle cells under a microscope, as well as the word 'myopathy,' which meaning muscle illness. Minicore myopathy symptoms are frequently present from birth, however diagnosis may not occur for several years. Symptoms can appear at any age, even maturity. Multicore myopathy, multi-minicore disease (MmD), and multi-minicore myopathy are all terms used to describe minicore myopathy. External ophthalmoplegia is a myopathic symptom of mitochondrial illness that can manifest itself in a variety of clinical conditions. However, an observant clinician's timely identification of EO can aid in the appropriate diagnosis of multi-organ mitochondrial sequelae, resulting in lower morbidity and death for these patients.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

None to be declared.

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